

YOUTH INVOLVEMENT IN ATHLET

Sevinch Onğarova

*Jizzakh State Pedagogical University
Student of Stage 3 of the Faculty of Physical Culture*

Abstract. *this article expresses our theoretical views on the involvement, interest and selection of students in the sport of athletics*

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Introduction. Athletics is one of the most popular sports. To achieve high levels of athletic skill in various sports, including athletics, early specialization of young athletes involves the use of a large volume of both specialized and general developmental exercises. However, there are several shortcomings in the system of training young athletes, one of which is the lack of good basic general physical preparation. Additionally, experience shows that systematic intensive training of children and adolescents during the early stages of sports training and the correct selection of athletes for successful participation in competitions in a particular type of athletics does not always yield the desired results. An incorrect choice of sports direction for children and adolescents leads to significant losses, harms the child's psyche, and does not allow for improving the quality of the training process. It is known that identifying individuals capable of achieving high athletic results in a chosen sport requires a long-term multi-stage process (several years) to determine specialization capabilities.

In recent years, there has been a growing trend of searching for new methodological approaches to diagnosing sports talent, allowing for more effective prediction of an athlete's achievements. Tests are increasingly being used in the selection process, helping coaches objectively assess various aspects of young athletes' training and make positive conclusions. To improve the effectiveness of preparing sports reserves, it is advisable to introduce a collective working method between coaches and physical education teachers in general education schools, who, in turn, should provide talented children to youth and sports school departments. Currently, attracting, interesting, and selecting children for athletics is very challenging, leading many coaches to consider how to make the right selections.

Moreover, the great scholar Abu Ali Ibn Sina recommended using exercises such as gymnastics, swimming, wrestling, brisk walking, running, jumping, spear throwing, and weight lifting in the treatment of patients. Our great ancestor, the conqueror Amir Temur, regularly used athletics exercises such as running on uneven terrain (cross-country), spear throwing, stone throwing, and hurdle jumping to train his soldiers to be physically strong, agile, and resilient. [1]

It is known that the effectiveness of sports training largely depends on the skillful selection of means and methods for physical education of children. However, there is no consensus on this issue. Many methodological manuals present the methodology for initial training mainly in the form of general rules. An essential element of the training methodology is the optimal regulation of physical activity according to the age, gender, and physical readiness of the athletes. First of all, a coach working with young athletes must know a lot: physiology, pedagogy, anatomy, biomechanics, the

functional characteristics of the growing body, and understanding and delicately handling the child's fragile psychology. Ideas taken from the experience of training older athletes can produce good results in training young athletes. It ensures a rapid increase in the results of competitive activity. However, in this case, a solid foundation of readiness is not formed. There are various opinions on the means and methods of physical education for young athletes: some authors believe that various sports and outdoor games should be used in training children. Others recommend using different sports as a means of general physical education. Still, others suggest including a large number of general developmental exercises in lessons along with games. These contradictory opinions indicate that a unified program for using the initial training tools and methods for young athletes has not yet been developed.

An essential aspect of organizing a training program for young athletes is considering participants' age characteristics, analyzing the child's maturity, and matching biological and chronological age. Specialists recommend undergoing comprehensive physical preparation before starting specialized training in the chosen type of athletics. A set of general developmental exercises selected correctly and effectively used can serve the goals of basic training. They act as a means to enhance the overall performance of body systems, develop strength, speed, and endurance, increase joint mobility, and improve coordination abilities.

Athletics can be practiced year-round. For this reason, athletics exercises (walking, running, jumping, and throwing) constitute a significant part of the special test complexes called "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy." Athletics is rightly called the "queen of sports." Its disciplines occupy a worthy place in national and international competitions and the Olympic Games program, with the most significant number of medals at stake. [2]

Starting from school education, embedding physical education and sports into young students can lead to the emergence of well-rounded, strong, active, and healthy future athletes in our country. Monitoring the training of young athletes helps increase the intensity of their training and develop their physical qualities during the training process. By regulating the exercises, methods, and intensity used, and maintaining constant control, a program can be developed to enhance results in the chosen type of athletics. Regular athletics exercises strengthen the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, ensure the harmonious development of muscles, improve joint mobility, and enhance neuromuscular coordination. Athletics training is conducted in physical education classes at school and school sports clubs. The content of athletics training for children, adolescents, and young people depends on their age characteristics, which must be considered when planning and conducting training. The significance of athletics exercises lies in their wide application during school sports club training sessions and summer camps. Many exercises are included in the "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" special test complexes through athletics disciplines. An individual engaged in athletics can achieve success in many other sports.

Interest in athletics training and self-confidence should be gradually reinforced through hard work. It is necessary to continuously explain that success in sports cannot be achieved without overcoming difficulties and working extremely hard. The teacher should instill a love for work in students by assigning tasks during training (performing exercises the required number of times, covering the distance within the set time, mastering a technical element). Accomplishing achievable tasks strengthens self-confidence and fosters a work ethic. Failures, especially at the initial stage, can have a negative impact. [3]

Our experience shows that during lessons and training, the attitude of school teachers towards students often leads to disorderly behavior during exercises, which in turn diminishes students' interest in clubs. Therefore, during training, we can help students master athletic movements by incorporating outdoor games while teaching various athletics disciplines.

For example, games like "Passing the Filled Ball," "Speed," "Who is Quicker," "Running

Over Hurdles," "Long Jump," and "High Jump" can greatly contribute to developing athletic qualities in students. These games play a significant role in shaping qualities like strength, speed, and flexibility. [4]

In conclusion, to attract young people to athletics and promote a healthy lifestyle, we must first organize practical training from the general education level. We must also establish sports competitions and accumulate sufficient knowledge and information to assess general and specific physical preparedness.

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